

HISTORY OF KESH SCIENTISTS WHO WORKED IN THE MIDDLE AGES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the lives and activities of the scholars from Kesh who made significant contributions to our national spiritual heritage as highlighted in historical sources.

Keywords: spiritual heritage, historical source, Kesh, science, scientists.

Throughout ancient history, many scholars and intellectuals have emerged from our current homeland, contributing significantly to the development of global science. Among them are renowned scholars born and raised in the rich historical region of Kashkadarya, whose works are recognized and celebrated even beyond our borders.

Kesh-Shahrisabz, often referred to as the "Dome of Knowledge and Literature," has produced numerous scholars whose names are recorded in various historical sources and who have made their mark through their works. The period from the 9th to the 12th centuries was a time of flourishing science in the Turan region, and Kesh was home to many prolific scholars.

One notable figure is the hadith scholar, commentator, and historian Najmiddin Umar ibn Muhammad ibn Ahmad an-Nasafiy (1069-1142), who recounts the lives and works of nine scholars from Kesh in his book "Al Qand fi Zikri Ulama" ("A Sweet Book on the Remembrance of the Scholars of Samarkand"). Among these scholars, Abd ibn Humayd ibn Nasr Keshiy (Keshiy) holds a special place.

Additional information about this hadith scholar, linguist, and jurist, as well as references to works by Shamsiddin Zahabi, who published "Siyar a'lam an-nubala" in Beirut in 1302, "Tarikh al-Islam" by Khatib al-Baghdadi, and "Al-Maktobat ash-Shomila" by Abu Muhammad Mahmud ibn Muso Ahmad ibn Husayn G'aytobiy Hanafi, among others, is also provided.

Abd ibn Humayd Keshiy (786-863) is considered one of the earliest hadith scholars from the region of Movarounnahr. He traveled extensively to places such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Baghdad, Basra, Kufa, Shom, Naysabur (Nishapur), Mecca, and Medina to acquire knowledge from numerous scholars. According to Shamsiddin Zahabi, he traveled to over two hundred locations in pursuit of learning. He gained deep knowledge in various fields and authored several works.

Among his notable writings are "Kitab ala Xuruf al-Mu'jam" ("Book on Letters"), "At-Tasarif" ("Morphology"), and "Kitab Fa'ltu wa Af'altu" ("A Book on the Types of Verbs"), as well as works related to hadith and Islamic theology like "Tafsir al-Kabir" and "Musnad al-Kabir."

One of the prominent scholars born and raised in Kesh during the 5th century Hijri is Abu Shakur Muhammad ibn Abdullah as-Said ibn Shuayb as-Solimiy al-Keshiy. His personality and scientific-spiritual legacy are referenced in the works of several comprehensive scholars. Notably, the book "Kashfu-z-Zunnun" by Khoji Khalifa, as well as research by European Orientalists such as K. Brockelmann, B. Madelung, Yu.U. Rudolf, and scholars from our own

country like Shaykh Abdulaziz Mansur, Ashirbek Mo'minov, and Saidmuxtor Oqilov, discuss him. Shamsiddin Muhammad Keshiy was a scholar, mystic, and Sufi who traveled from Kesh to Iran in pursuit of knowledge and was buried there. One of his notable works is "Kitab al-Hadi fi al-Nahm" ("Arabic Grammar"). He had many students, one of whom was Qutbiddin Mahmud bin Ma'sud bin Muslix Sheroziy, who became a well-known scholar in Iran. Detailed information about Shamsiddin Muhammad Keshiy can also be found in the "Lug'atnoma," a book published in Iran.

Mushtoq Shahrizabziy, Mulla Qurbon Xiromiy, Mirzo Umrboqiy Shahrizabziy (Samarqandiy), and Farax Shahrizabziy are among the creative figures of the 19th century.

Abdulkarim Fazliy Namangoniy describes Mushtoq Shahrizabziy in his work "Majmuai Shoiron" as a true poet, noting that he lived and worked in Qo'qon for several years. Mushtoq is known for his beautiful and exquisite ghazals and rubaiyat.

Mulla Qurbon Xiromiy, born in the city of Kitob, composed several epic poems, including "Chor Darvesh," "To'tinoma," "Ra'no va Zebo," and "Yusuf va Zulayho."

The poet, scholar, and translator Abdulla Rahmonov Gulshaniy spent many years of his life in the Qamashi district. His two-volume work "Gulistoni Gulshaniy" and a three-volume collection of Tajik poetry have been left as his legacy. Abdulla Gulshaniy was also a skilled calligrapher and an adept translator of Persian works.

Fayzulloxo'ja Ravnaqiy, Ismoilxon Faqiriy, and Najmiddinxon Asiriy are representatives of a related family lineage. Detailed information about them can be found in the comprehensive dictionary titled "Islam in the Former Russian Empire," published in Moscow, and in the book "Index of Works in the Ravnaqiy Shahrizabziy Library," published in Qom, Iran.

In this scholarly article, we have discussed various scholars and poets who emerged from ancient Kesh. However, we are aware that there are still many figures whose manuscripts await study, and whose lives and works remain inadequately explored and unpublished. Thus, significant responsibilities lie ahead for our scholars and researchers in this field.

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